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THE POLITICS OF CITIZENSHIP AMENDMENT BILL 2019 AND THE QUESTION OF MANIPUR

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1. Issue

The issue of citizenship in India has been an intriguing one since the time of its conception as a socio-political reality. The partition of the erstwhile British India into Pakistan and India primarily on the basis of religion had shown seeds of hatred, violence and suspicion amongst the two countries. After suffering from various forms of oppression and exploitation under the same colonial regime for more than two centuries, the 1947 partition set off the basis of an engagement which becomes institutionalised between India and Pakistan. The politics surrounding mass exodus that took place

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into each country's territory emerged as one of the many protracted issues that continue to influence the socio-political landscape of the sub-continent later. The policy to re-introduce the Citizenship Amendment Bill (CAB) 2019 by the ruling political party has once again brought to the fore – the fundamental question of Manipur's survival as a distinct people and culture under the existing scheme of India's polity. The CAB carries with it the potential of a population bomb with the intention of completely wiping out the indigenous populations of Manipur and other North Eastern states. It seeks to legalise unabated influx of non-Muslim Bangladeshis in the region by entitling them citizenship rights. The opposition to CAB is not for its anti-secular character but for its possible ramifications to the indigenous populations of Manipur and their endurance as a civilizational entity. Come CAB in an altogether secular form, Manipuri people still have a fundamental right to oppose it in toto. In this backdrop, we remind ourselves of the historical and political consequences which India-Manipur relations have been brought upon the people of Manipur.

The illegal annexation of the erstwhile independent Asiatic State of Manipur by the Republic of India in 1949, has persistently posed tremendous challenges to the collective co-existence of Manipur as a historical, political and cultural reality. This is not a mere hypothetical allegation but a statement of fact which is founded upon a critical analysis of the systematic policies institutionalised by the Indian state. With the taking over of the then Administration of Manipur and termination of the Manipur Legislative Assembly in total contravention of the Indian Independence Act, 1947 (IIA); Manipur Constitution Act, 1947; UN Charter and norms of customary international law, the Government of India scrapped the Permit System in November, 1950 leading to opening of floodgates to unabated influx of foreigners to the region. As per the analysis of census data, the number of illegal immigrants or non-indigenous persons has shot up to 10 lakhs in 2011 as against 3000 during 1948-50. In the absence of influx protection mechanism, this number of the non-indigenous persons in Manipur is bound to shoot up to

unimaginable proportions. Tripura presents a clear example where influx population had driven the indigenous communities out of their own homeland. India's CAB seeks to encourage these phenomena in Manipur and the whole of North Eastern region. This bill if it becomes a law in its present form can wipe out the identity of the whole population of Manipur and can complete the Indian aggression that began in 1949.

2. Citizenship Amendment Bill– Historical Burden of India's Partition

The issue of citizenship seems to possess a character which the authority of the Indian State cannot conveniently ignore. India's responsibility transcends any categorisation of political affiliation or ideologies. This argument finds support from the statements made by Indian nationalist leaders at the time of independence and also reflected in the debates of the Constituent Assembly. Thus, Pundit Jawaharlal Nehru stated *"We think also of our brothers and sisters who have been cut off from us by political boundaries and who unhappily cannot share at present in the freedom that has come. They are with us and will remain of us whatever may happen, and we shall be sharers of their good and ill-fortune alike"* (Speech on "Tryst with Destiny", 14 August 1947 at Parliament House). B.R. Ambedkar explaining article 5 of the Indian Constitution stated *"...It is not the object of this particular Article to lay down a permanent law of citizenship...The business of laying down permanent law of citizenship has been left to the Parliament, ...the entire matter regarding citizenship has been left to Parliament to determine by any law it may deem fit"*. He continued *"...If there is any category of people who are left out by the provisions in this amendment, we have given power to Parliament subsequently to make provision for them"* (CADs, 10 August, 1949). These concerns find clear expression in article 11 thus: **"Parliament to regulate the right of citizenship by law – Nothing in the foregoing provisions of this Part shall derogate from the power of Parliament to make any provision with respect to the acquisition and termination of citizenship and all other matters relating to citizenship"**. Thus, the CAB reflects the historical

responsibility of the Indian State to redress the injustices of partition politics.

3. Manipur and the Citizenship Amendment Bill, 2019

Clause 2 of the CAB seeks to relax certain limitations on foreigners or persons who are considered foreigners under the laws concerning Foreigners and Passport in India. It seeks to legalise first, the stay of persons/foreigners who come into India without a valid passport or other travel document and second, those foreigners who entered into India with a valid passport or other travel document but which have expired permitted period of time. The implication is that foreigners without any of these valid documents can become Indian citizens through naturalisation process. The effect of the CAB in acquiring Indian citizenship through naturalisation process is that those foreigners/persons who have resided in India with the intention to stay permanently for not less than 6 years are eligible to become Indian citizens.

So far as the CAB seeks to grant citizenship to 6 communities such as Hindus, Sikhs, Jains, Buddhists, Parsis and Christians coming from Afghanistan, Bangladesh and Pakistan, there are reasonable apprehensions amongst regions of India such as northeast for their cultural and linguistic survival. The indigenous communities of the north-east compared to other states of India are backward in several aspects such as population growth rate, socioeconomic development, etc. The apprehensions for a demographic invasion in the NE region in case CAB becomes a law is serious and founded upon the practical consciousness of the peoples inhabiting the region. For instance, Assam has been flooded with Bangladeshi migrants after the 1971 Bangladesh-Pakistan war. The Assam Accord concluded in 1985 reflects the seriousness.

Section 6 A of the Citizenship Act, 1955 is of special import here for it provides a testimony to the fact that the Bangladeshi war of 1971 had the most deleterious effect on the socio-political demography of Assam, a space

that has the propensity to influence and shape the social, political, economic, cultural, linguistic stability of the entire region known as North-east of India. Any changes in the socio-cultural demography of Assam are representative of its far reaching implications in the neighbouring landscapes. Tripura became a fallacy to the guarantees of tribal identity protection. So is the case with Inner Line Protected States such as Nagaland, Arunachal Pradesh and Mizoram. Outsider or immigrant populations have made these states their safe places to live in, earn income and gradually overtake the local population due to the latter's marginal, divided and regressive socio-economic, cultural and political formations. In no time, Bangladeshi migrants who initially provided a taken for granted electoral base, later became to dominate the political, bureaucratic and cultural space of the region. The question that drives home the point is on what basis Manipur shares this historical and political responsibility of India's partition? Partition took place 2 years before India illegally annexed the State of Manipur. Where does Manipur stand in the Indian policy of restitution for partition? What is the rationale of the nexus between India's CAB and Manipur sharing the former's historical responsibility?

Manipur's existence as a historical and political reality, distinct and separate from the Republic of India and as had been testified by the *Anglo – Manipur Treaty of 4 September 1762* and the *Treaty of Yandaboo of 24 February 1826* do not support this theory of sharing India's historical responsibility. For a brief period of 56 years, Manipur was brought within the fold of British India by the Anglo – Manipur War, 1891. However, after the Indian Independence Act (IIA) was enacted by the British Parliament, Manipur and other Princely States became independent by virtue of its Section 7 (1) (b). This has been repeatedly re-affirmed by the Supreme Court of India in a number of cases such as (i) *Virendra Singh v. State of U.P.* (1954); (ii) *The States of Saurashtra v. Memom Haji Ismai* (1959); (iii) *Sarwarlal v. States of Hyderabad* (1960); (iv) *State of Gujarat v. VoraFiddali* (1964); (v) *Shri Ragunathrao Ganpatrao v. Union of India* (1993) etc.

Section 7 (1) (b) of the IIA in line with the United Nations Charter norm of Article 2 (1) put Manipur and India on an equal juridical plane. Leave alone the idea of sharing India's partition responsibility, the people of Manipur had persistently denounced the Treaty of Shillong (Merger Agreement) signed on 21st September 1949 between the Dominion Government of India and titular Head of Manipur State, Maharajah Bodhchandra as illegal and unconstitutional a number of times: first, the Manipur Legislative Assembly on 28th September 1949 (Fourth Sitting of the Third Session); second, by the Manipur People's National Convention held on 28-29 October 1993; third, by the National Seminar on Human Rights held on 8 and 9 December, 1994. The Republic of India in its Constitution gives due recognition to this historical and political distinctiveness of Manipur in Sl. No. 19 of the First Schedule thus: "*The territory which immediately before the commencement of this Constitution was being administered as if it were a Chief Commissioner's Province under the name of Manipur*".

3.1. Manipur under Uti Possidetis Juris

Even within the present constitutional scheme of India's polity, Manipur represents the case of *Uti Possidetis Juris*. No provision of the Constitution of India that seeks to dismember or alter her territorial, social, cultural and linguistic indigenous integrity can apply to the state of Manipur. The basis of the principle of *uti possidetis juris* is the 'intangibility of frontiers inherited from colonisation'. Its application has the effect of freezing the territorial title existing at the moment of independence to produce the 'photograph of the territory' at the critical date. The Chamber of the International Court in *Burkina Faso v. Republic of Mali* (International Court of Justice Reports, 1986) characterised *uti possidetis juris* – "The essence of the principle lies in its primary aim of securing respect for the territorial boundaries at the moment when independence is achieved. Such territorial boundaries might be no more than delimitations between different administrative divisions or colonies all subject to the same

sovereign. In that case, the application of the principle of *uti possidetis* resulted in administrative boundaries being transformed into international frontiers in the full sense of the term”. *Uti possidetis juris* resists to protect Manipur’s boundary as stood at the time of the enactment of the IIA. Indian Parliament does not have the legal and political proprietary to alter the integrity of Manipur in its holistic sense. The Indian Parliament has an unaddressed agenda of according Manipur a constitutional provision similar to article 370 which can provide the legal mechanism to effectuate the recognition given under Sl. No. 19, First Schedule of the Constitution of India.

3.1.1. Uti Possidetis Juris: Beyond Territoriality

Article 2(4) norm of the UN Charter informs India’s serious obligations to respect Manipur’s identity and to refrain from resorting to threats or use of force against its territorial integrity. Theories of political independence and territoriality are basically founded upon the concepts of “*population or people*”. A population is identified with the culture and languages of its social groups. Cultural and linguistic identity of the people is thus central to the ideas of polity, territory, and sovereignty. Protection of a territory without safeguarding the social values, culture and identity of the inhabitants living therein is to defeat the intent, objectives and purposes of the article 2 (4) norm that prohibits the use of force against the territorial integrity or political independence of sovereign states. This is where the *uti possidetis juris* rule becomes relevant to Manipur beyond its classical territorial dimension. Under this rule of contemporary customary international law (*Burkina Faso v. Republic of Mali, 1986*), the Government of India cannot apply policies such as CAB that tends to or will bring substantial changes to the demography so as to result in the total disruption of the social, cultural, and linguistic identity of the people of Manipur. Substantial disruption here would mean altering or diluting those values without which the “idea of Manipuri” will no longer survive. The demographic composition, cultural and linguistic identity of a people at the moment of independence from colonial power is protected by *uti*

possidetis juris. India cannot disturb Manipur's linguistic and cultural integrity under any circumstances. Manipur's indigeneity – aboriginal population, culture, identity and political aspirations falls within the protected values of the international community. So far as the CAB seeks to decimate the indigenous socio-cultural, linguistic integrity and subsequently to repress political aspirations, the Indian state is in the process of blatant and forceful deprivation of the right of Manipuri people to self-determination which constitutes a norm of *jus cogens*. Application of the CAB to Manipur with or without any exception contravenes India's obligations under article 2 (4) of the UN Charter and *jus cogens norms*.

4. Citizen Amendment Bill, 2019 and International Humanitarian Law

The CAB underlines the agenda of the Government of India to systematically disturb and alter the indigenous integrity of Manipur. CAB is not less than a population bomb **genocidal** in intent and character seeking to annihilate the indigenous Manipuri population the movement or settlement of non-indigenous populations into Manipur, international humanitarian law becomes relevant. Article 49 of the Fourth Geneva Convention relative to the Protection of Civilians in Times of War of 12 August 1949 to which India is a High Contracting State party, provides: “*The occupying Power (India) shall not deport or transfer parts of its own civilian population into the territory (Manipur) it occupies*” (Parentheses added). The principle underlying the protection of human dignity of the civilian population caught in the middle of a conflict under Article 3 common to the Four Geneva Conventions is also to safeguard the demographic integrity of the people concerned. The Indian state cannot transfer or implant population in Manipur. Besides the operation of *uti possidetis juris* in favour of Manipur, population transfer or implantation is absolutely prohibited as a *war crime* under article 8 (2) (b) (viii) of the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, thus: “*The transfer, directly or indirectly, by the Occupying Power (India) of parts of its own civilian population into the territory (Manipur) it occupies*”. Article 25 (1) & (2), Rome Statute reinforces

the severity of this war crime with individual criminal responsibility – whoever incites whether directly or indirectly in the commission of the war crime of population movement or transfer in the occupied territory of Manipur can be prosecuted for individual criminal responsibility.

5. Conclusion

One of the appealing serious and yet erroneous assumptions regarding CAB is the insertion of a clause to provide for exemption from the extent and scope of CAB with respect to Manipur and North-eastern states. The question is both political and legal. Considering the fact that exception clauses in central legislations are found to have been provided let's say for the states of Jammu and Kashmir under special constitutional arrangements such as Article 370 and for Nagaland under Article 371A of the Indian constitution, the question that needs critical engagement with respect to Manipur remains – what context justifies the insertion of such an exemption clause and on what grounds. In the case of Jammu & Kashmir, it must be noted that Article 370 read with Article 35(A) is reflection of the commitment of the Government of India towards the State of Jammu & Kashmir due to the nature of its historical and political association with the Indian Union. Under the Instrument of Accession, Jammu & Kashmir agreed to join India provided special provisions are guaranteed. Article 370 and Article 35A stand to reflect that core understanding between the Indian Union and State of Jammu & Kashmir. Central legislations of India are not automatically applicable unless the State Legislature of Jammu & Kashmir adopts a resolution in that regard. Similarly, for the State of Nagaland, based on the Shillong Accord, Parliamentary laws which can impinge upon certain areas are not readily functional to the state. For these two States and their respective constitutional provisions there had been political contexts that resulted into the insertion of such arrangements outside the constitutional norm of

general applicability of Parliamentary laws. Even with respect to the State of Assam, section 6A of the Citizenship Act, 1955 was a result of the Assam Accord where the Government of India committed itself to detect and deport Bangladeshis who entered into Assam as a result of the Bangladeshi war of liberation in 1971. These provisions stand to inform us that there had been compelling political circumstances that bought the conviction of the Indian parliament to exempt certain states from the general norm of extent and applicability.

In case of Manipur, the only provision under the Constitution of India which provides constitutional testimony to Manipur's existence as a historical and political entity that preceded India's polity is Sl. No. 19 of the First Schedule. Apart from this provision, no political and social movements have so far succeeded in concluding an agreement or entering into an arrangement that seeks to safeguard Manipur's existence and its organic integrity from India's laws and policies such as the proposed CAB. Another point of concern which calls for serious engagement is the effectiveness of such exemption clauses guaranteed to Jammu & Kashmir and state of Nagaland –how far have these constitutional mechanisms been able to safeguard and protect the interests of the people of these two states which it sought to achieve? India's policy of one nation, one market and one constitution or one law tends to render these constitutional mechanisms into dilution and without little effect. The resolutions adopted by the protected states of Nagaland and Mizoram during the region-wide protest against the CAB stands to present us these questions. Then, where lies the solution to our problems.

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